

BAM File Extraction Manual Using the IonTorrent Suite VariantCaller Plugin

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1. Introduction

The VariantCaller Plugin within the IonTorrent Suite is a tool designed for identifying genetic variants in next-generation sequencing data. However, in our case, we will primarily use it to remove primer sequences from raw sequencing reads.

This manual focuses on the steps required to extract BAM (Binary Alignment Map) files after running the VariantCaller Plugin. These BAM files will already contain the reads after primer trimming has been performed.

Depending on the version of the IonTorrent Suite being used, some of the steps described in this document may differ.

2. Prerequisites

Before starting, ensure that you have the following:

- A functional installation of the IonTorrent Suite.
- Sequencing data prepared and uploaded to the IonTorrent platform.
- Appropriate permissions to execute plugins within the platform.

3. Environment Setup

To configure your working environment:

1. **Access the IonTorrent Platform:** Log in to your IonTorrent platform account.
2. **Prepare Your Data:** Ensure that the sequencing data has been properly uploaded and is available within the system.
3. **Select the Experiment:** Navigate to the experiment containing the data you wish to analyse.

4. Steps to Run the VariantCaller Plugin

1. **Navigate to the Plugins Section:**
 - Within the IonTorrent platform interface, go to the “*Plugins*” section.
2. **Select VariantCaller:**
 - Locate and select the VariantCaller Plugin from the list of available plugins.
 - Ensure that it is marked as “*Enabled*”. It can also be configured to run automatically for every sequencing run by selecting “*Select by Default*”.
3. **Configure the Analysis:**
 - Choose the analysis parameters. Make sure to configure the options appropriate for your experiment, such as the type of variants to identify (SNPs, indels, etc.).

The screenshot shows the 'Configure Plugin' interface for the 'Torrent Variant Caller'. It features a 'Submit' button at the top left. Below it is a configuration dropdown menu (1) with the value 'Current 1bc9e8f0-849a-4056-80e6-7dd1da6e528c' and a 'Manage Configurations/Barcodes' link (2). The main settings are organized into sections: 'Chip Type' (Proton PI), 'Library Type' (AmpliSeq), 'Variant Frequency' (Germ Line), 'AmpliSeq Panel' (Unspecified), 'Reference Genome' (As Specified in the Plan for Each Barcode), 'Targeted Regions' (As Specified in the Plan for Each Barcode), 'Hotspot Regions' (As Specified in the Plan for Each Barcode), and 'Parameter Settings' (Generic - Proton P1 - Germ Line - Low Stringency). There are buttons for 'Add panel...' (4), 'Add targets...' (5), and 'Add hotspots...' (6). At the bottom, there are buttons for 'Load external parameter file' (8) and 'Copy selected setting to Custom' (9), and a 'Show Advanced Settings' dropdown (10). A 'Configuration Name' field with a 'Save' button is at the bottom left (7).

1. Configuration: A reusable predefined or custom VariantCaller configuration containing settings for a reference genome, target regions, hotspots, and parameter settings.

2. Manage Configurations / Barcodes

3. Configurations included in a predefined or custom configuration

4. Add Panel

5. Add Targets

6. Add Hotspots

7. Configuration Name

8. Load External Parameter File

9. Copy Selected Configuration to Custom

10. Show Advanced Settings

4. **Specify Input Files:**

- Select the sequencing files that will be used as input for the analysis.

5. **Run the Plugin:**

- Click “Run” to start the analysis.

Create a Custom Configuration for the VariantCaller Plugin

You can create a custom configuration to reuse the next time the plugin is run manually. The custom configuration can be applied to the entire VariantCaller run or to individual barcodes included in the run.

- Under the “Datos” tab, click “Ejecuciones” and then “Reportes Completados”.
- Click on the Report Name corresponding to the completed sequencing run.
- Click “Plugins”, then select “Plugins para Ejecutar”.
- In the “Seleccionar un Plugin para Ejecutar” dialog box, choose “VariantCaller” plugin and click “Configurar”.
- Once you have finished configuring all settings, enter a name in the “Nombre de Configuración” field and click “Guardar”.

5. BAM File Extraction

Once the analysis has completed, the BAM files will be available for extraction.

Follow these steps:

_07_40_user_GSS5PL-0064-494-240610-LIB104-SARS_CoV2

ionXpress_001
99935831
ion_ampliseq_sars-cov-2-insight
Ampliseq
Enabled
Ion_AmpliSeq_SARS-CoV-2-Insight.20210329.designed BED
None
Ion_AmpliSeq_SARS-CoV-2-Insight.20210329.designed_effective
BED
Generic - S5/S5XL (510/520/530) - Germ Line - Low Stringency
germline_low_stringency_510_520_530, TS version: 5.12
tvc 5.12-28 (d8e0d81) Parameters File

Mapped Reads: BAM, BAI
TVC-Processed Reads: BAM, BAI
Variant Calls: VCF.GZ, VCF.GZ.TBI, XLS, COV
Variants + Non-Variant Coverage: gVCF.GZ, gVCF.GZ.TBI
View Variant Calls in IGV: IGV
Deprecated Features: Classic
Documentation: Torrent Variant Caller Documentation

to Allele Name Gene ID Region Name Allele Source
Var Freq to % Total Cov ≥

Ref	Variant	Allele Call	Frequency	Quality	Subset Of	Variant Type	Allele Source	Allele Name	Gene ID
C	T	Homozygous	100.0 %	2944.3	---	SNP	Novel	tvc.novel.1	r1
C	T	Homozygous	100.0 %	772.2	---	SNP	Novel	tvc.novel.2	r1

1. Access the Analysis Results

- Navigate to the experiment results page where the VariantCaller Plugin was executed.
- 2. Locate the BAM Files**
 - Within the analysis results, locate the generated BAM files. These files contain the sequence alignments and, since primer trimming has already been performed, they are essential for downstream bioinformatics analysis.
- 3. Download the BAM Files**
 - Select the BAM files labelled TVC-Processed Reads for download.
 - Typically, you will find an option to download them directly by clicking the area highlighted in the image, or to export the files to a specific storage system.
 - Optional: Verify File Integrity
 - After downloading, it is recommended to verify the integrity of the BAM files.
 - If you are familiar with the command line, you can use tools such as `samtools`:

```
samtools quickcheck -v sample.bam
```

6. Common Troubleshooting

Below are some common issues and their solutions:

- **The Plugin Does Not Run:** Verify that you have the appropriate user permissions and ensure that the input data is correct.
- **BAM Files Are Not Generated:** Review the analysis parameters and confirm that they are appropriate for your data type. Also ensure that the analysis completed successfully without errors.

7. Additional Resources

For further information and support, please consult the following resources:

- Official Ion Torrent Documentation: [IonTorrent 5.16 Documentation](#)